

BACILLUS THURINGIENSIS IFO SHTAMMINING KO'SAK QURTIGA FAOLLIGI VA MOLEKULAYAR XARAKTERISTIKASI

Qobilov Fazliddin

O'zRFA Mikrobiologiya instituti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston.

Email: fazliddinbiology@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8372635>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur tadqiqot ishida, *B.thuringiensis*ning yangi tabiiy shtammining molekulyar genetik identifikatsiyasi va *Lepidoptera* oilasiga mansub zararkunanda hasharotlarga qarshi faol bo'lgan *cry* (kristal) va *vip* (vegetativ insektitsid oqsil) oqsillarini kodlovchi genlarni aniqlash haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Bunda, 16S rDNK identifikatsiyasi bo'yicha mazkur shtamm *B.thuringiensis* turiga yaqin ekanligi aniqlandi va *B.thuringiensis* Ifo shtammi deb nomlandi. Bundan tashqari, *BtIfo* shtammida *cry1* oilasining *cry1Aa*, *cry1Ac* va *vip3* genlari, hamda *cry2* oilasi ham uchrashligi tajribalar davomida aniqlandi va bu genlar *Lepidoptera* hasharotlarga qarshi faollikka ega bo'lgan *cry1Aa*, *cry1Ac* va *vip3A* oqsillarini kodlashi adabiyotlardan ma'lum bo'ldi. Shuningdek, *BtIfo* shtammi *Helicoverpa armigera* hasharotining 2-3 yoshli lichinkalariga qarshi faolligi o'rganilganda 7 kun ichida 100% lichinkalar nobud bo'lganligi laboratoriya tajribalarida qayd etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Bacillus thuringiensis*, identifikatsiya, *cry*, *vip* genlari, *Lepidoptera*, δ -endotoksinlar.

Abstract. In this study, molecular genetic identification of a new native strain of *B.thuringiensis* and identification of genes encoding *cry* (crystal) and *vip* (vegetative insecticidal protein) proteins active against harmful insects belonging to the *Lepidoptera* family are presented. In this case, according to 16S rDNA identification, this strain was found to be close to *B.thuringiensis* species and was named *B.thuringiensis* Ifo strain. In addition, in the *BtIfo* strain, *cry1Aa*, *cry1Ac*, and *vip3* genes of the *cry1* family, as well as the *cry2* family, were found during the researches, and it was known from the literature that these genes encode *Cry1Aa*, *Cry1Ac*, and *Vip3A* proteins, which have activity against lepidopteran insects. Also, when the activity of the *BtIfo* strain on 2-3-year-old larvae of *Helicoverpa armigera* insect was studied, it was noted in laboratory experiments that 100% of the larvae died within 7 days.

Keywords: *Bacillus thuringiensis*, identification, *Cry*, *Vip* genes, *Lepidoptera*, δ -endotoxins.

Аннотация. В работе представлена молекулярно-генетическая идентификация нового природного штамма *B. thuringiensis* и идентификация генов, кодирующих белки *cry* (кристаллический) и *vip* (вегетативный инсектицидный белок), активные в отношении вредных насекомых семейства *Lepidoptera*. При этом по данным идентификации 16S рДНК этот штамм оказался близким к виду *B. thuringiensis* и получил название штамма *B. thuringiensis* Ifo. Кроме того, у штамма *BtIfo* в ходе экспериментов были обнаружены гены *cry1Aa*, *cry1Ac* и *vip3* семейства *cry1*, а также семейства *cry2*, причем из литературы известно, что эти гены кодируют *cry1Aa*, *cry1Ac* и *vip3A* белки, обладающие активностью в отношении чешуекрылых насекомых. Также при изучении активности штамма *BtIfo* на 2-3-летних личинках насекомого *Helicoverpa Armigera* в лабораторных экспериментах было отмечено, что 100% личинок погибали в течение 7 дней.

Ключевые слова: *Bacillus thuringiensis*, идентификация, *cry*, гены *vip*, чешуекрылые, δ -эндотоксины.

Bacillus thuringiensis (Bt) aerob, spora hosil qiluvchi, gram-musbat va entomopatogen bakteriya parasporal kristall oqsillar yoki δ -endotoksinlar (Cry) hosil qiladi. Ushbu Cry oqsillari Lepidoptera, Coleoptera va Diptera kabi hasharotlar zararkunandalari uchun zaharli hisoblanadi [1, 2]. Cry, Cyt va Vip oqsillari tarkibiga asoslanib, har bir shtamm lepidopteran, dipteran, koleopteran yoki hymenopteran zararkunandalariga va hatto kanalar va nematodalar kabi boshqa umurtqasiz hayvonlarga nisbatan faolligi aniqlangan [3, 1, 2]. 1985 yildan 2019 yilgacha 30 yildan ortiq izlanishlardan va skriningdan so'ng, 300 dan ortiq yangi Cry oqsillari aniqlandi va Cry1 dan Cry80 gacha tasniflanadi [4]. Butun dunyoda lepidopteran zararkunandalari har yili qishloq xo'jaligi hosildorligiga katta iqtisodiy zararlarni keltirib chiqaradi [5]. *Helicoverpa armigera* lichinkalari g'o'zaning novdalari va barglari va kurtaklarini yeb, paxta hosilini kamaytiradi [6]. Yo'qotishlarni kamaytirish uchun asosiy lepidopteran zararkunandalariga qarshi kurashda *Bacillus thuringiensis*ni ifodalovchi g'o'za navlari keng qo'llaniladi [7].

Ko'sak qurti (*Helicoverpa armigera*) O'zbekistonda asosan Farg'ona, Andijon, Namangan, Toshkent viloyatlari paxta maydonlariga jiddiy zarar yetkazadi. Boshqa viloyatlarda nisbatan zarari kam. Lekin 2020-yila Qashqadaryo viloyatining Nishon, Mirishkor, tumanlarida ham sezilarli zarar yetkazgan. G'o'zadan tashqari pomidor, makkajo'xori, baqlajon, no'xat va dukkakli ekinlarga juda qattiq zarar yetkazadi. Qarshi kurash ishlari o'tkazilmasa 20-30% gacha hosilga zarar yetkazadi. Umuman karshi kurashilmasa 60-80% gacha zararlaydi. O'rtacha qattik zarar keltirgan yillari 30% gacha zarar yetkazadi.

Bt Ifo shtammini *Helicoverpa armigera* lichinkalariga qarshi sinash uchun avvalo mazkur shtamm Lauria-Bertani (LB) (1L:1% Tryptone, 0.5% Yeast Extract, 1% NaCl) suyuq ozuqa muhitiga ekildi. *Bt* Ifo shtammi spora va kristal oqsillari hosil bo'lgunga qadar tebratkichda 150 ay/daq, 30°C haroratda inkubatsiya qilindi. Spora va kristal hosil qilinishi mikroskopda tekshirib turildi. Yettinchi kunga kelib *Bt* Ifo shtammi to'liq spora va kristallar hosil qilgani kuzatildi (1 rasm).

Tayyor *Bt* Ifo tarkibli preparatni selder o'simligiga sepib, namlantirib *Helicoverpa armigera* ning 2-3 yoshli lichinkalari oziqlantirildi va yeti kun davomida kuzatildi (6-Rasm).

1-Rasm. *B.thuringiensis* Ifo shtammining spora va kristal oqsillarining mikroskopik ko'rinishi. A-spora; B-kristal oqsil.

B.thuringiensis Ifo shtammidan umumiy DNK ajratish: Laboratoriya kolleksiyasida mavjud 100 ga yaqin *B.thuringiensis* shtamlari orasidan Bt1fo shtammi mikroskopik tahlil orqali ya'ni kristal hosil qilishiga qarab tanlab olindi. Mazkur Bt1fo shtammining 16S rRNK geni bo'yicha molekulyar genetik identifikatsiyasi va cry, vip genlarini aniqlash uchun genom DNK si ajratish amalga oshirildi. Bunda modifikatsiyalan Marmur [8] usulidan foydalanildi. Buning uchun

Lauria-Bertani ozuqasida 16 soat davomida 37°C xaroratda o'sgan bakteriya kulturalari o'stirildi va DNK ajratildi (1-rasm).

Praymerlar tanlash: Bt1fo shtamning 16S rDNK identifikatsiyasi va cry, vip genlarini aniqlash uchun praymerlar dizayn qilindi. Dizayn qilingan praymerlar SnapGene dasturi yordamida tekshirib ko'rildi va IDT ([Integrated DNA Technologies](#)) firmasi tomonidan sintez qilindi (1-Jadval).

1-jadval

***B. thuringiensis* 1fo shtammidagi cry va vip genlarini aniqlash uchun praymerlar dizayn qilish**

Praymerlar nomi	Praymerlar ketma-ketligi	Gen nomi	J/A	Havolalar
cry1F cry1R	CATGATTCATGCGGCAGATAAC TTGTGACACTTCTGCTTCCCAT	cry1	274-277	[9]
cry2F cry2R	GTTATICTTAATGCAGATGAA TGGG CGGATAAAATAATCTGGGAA ATAGT	cry2	689-701	
cry3F cry3R	CGTTATCGCAGAGAGATGAC ATTAAC CATCTGTTGTTTCTGGAGGCA AT	Cry3Aa, -Ba, -Bb, -Ca	589-604	
cry4F cry4R	GCATATGATGTAGCGAAACA AGCC GCGTGACATACCCATTCCAG GTCC	cry4	439	
cry7-8F cry7-8R	AAGCAGTGAATGCCTTGTTTAC C CTTCTAAACCTTGACTACTT	cry7Aa, -Ab; cry8Aa, -Ba, - Ca	420-423	
Lep1A Lep1B	CCGGTGCTGGATTTGTGTTA AATCCCGTATTGTACCAGCG	cry1Aa, cry1Ab, cry1Ac	490	
Dip1A Dip1B	CAAGCCGCAAATCTTGTGGA ATGGCTTGTTTCGCTACATC	cry4A, cry4B	797	[10]
Col1A Col1B	GTCCGCTGTATATTCAGGTG CACTTAATCCTGTGACGCCT	cry3A	649	
5-	GGATCCGATGAAAAATATGA	vip1A	2300	

vip1A 3- vip1A	AGAA GTCGACTTATCTAGATTTGTT AGGT			[11]
5- vip2A 3- vip2A	GGATCCGATGAAAAGAATGG AGGG GTCGACTTAATTTGTTAATAA TGTTG	vip2A	1300	
vip3AF vip3AR	ATGAACAAGAATAATACTAA A GCGGCCGCTTACTTAATAGAG AC	vip3A	2300	[12]

B.thuringiensis 1fo shtamining 16S rRNK, Cry va Vip genlarining PZR amplifikatsiyasi: PZR amplifikatsiyasini amalga oshirishda universal oligonukleotid praymerlardan foydalanildi: 27F (AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG) va 1492R (GGTACCTTGTTACGACTT) [13]. Bakteriya shtamidan ajratilgan DNK na'munalari PZR-amplifikatsiyasi GenPak® PCR MasterMix kitida amalga oshirildi. Bunda, reaksiya umumiy 20 mkl miqdorida tayyorlanib, 10 mkl Dilution, 8,2 mkl ikki marta distillangan suv, 0,4 mkl dan (27F va 1492R) praymer va 1 mkl DNK namunalardan tarkib topdi. PZR amplifikatsiya optimizatsiyasi boshlang'ich denaturatsiya 94°C 3 daqiqa, denaturatsiya 94°C 40 soniya, odjig (primer annealing) 55°C 40 sekund, elongatsiya 70°C 90 soniya, yakuniy elongatsiya 70°C 10 daqiqa, davomida takroriy 35 siklda olib borildi. Amplikonlar etidium-bromid bilan bo'yalgan 2 % li agarozali gelda elektroforez yordamida deteksiya qilindi (2A-rasm).

B. thuringiensis 1fo shtamidagi cry va vip genlarini birlamchi PZR skriningi uchun 2x Green PCR Master Mix majmuasidan foydalanildi. Bu an'anaviy Taq DNK polimeraza bilan solishtirganda yuqori sezuvchanlik, uzunroq PCR mahsulotlari va yuqori rentabellikni ta'minlaydi (Thermo Fisher). Hamda, tadqiqotning keying bosqichlari ya'ni sekvins va klonlash usullarini amalga oshirish uchun genlarni to'liq sintez bo'lishini ham ta'minlaydi. Bunda PZR reaksiya umumiy 10 mkl ga tayyorlanib: 2x Green PCR MM-5mkl, ikki marta distillangan suv-3.4 mkl, forward-reverse praymerlar (1-Jadval) 0.3 mkl dan va shtamm genom DNK-1 mkl ni tashkil qildi. PZR amplifikatsiyadan chiqqan na'munalari 0.7% li agarozaga gelida ko'rildi (2B-rasm).

Sekvenslash uchun PZR mahsulotlari 2% agarozaga gelidan steril skalpel yordamida kesib olindi va QIAquick® Gel tozalash to'plami yordamida tozalandi [14]. Tozalangan PZR mahsulotlarining miqdori NanoDrop apparatida o'lchandi (NanoPhotometer® N60; IMPLLEN). PZR mahsulotlari Rossiyaning СИНТОЛИ firmasi tomonidan sekvins qilindi.

Bt1fo shtamining 16S rRNK, cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlarining ketma-ketlik natijalari NCBI BLAST ma'lumotlar bazasidagi turlar bilan o'zaro solishtirildi. (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/BLAST>). Bt1fo shtamining 16S rRNK, cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlarining ketma-ketlik natijalari NCBI BLAST ma'lumotlar bazasidagi turlar bilan o'zaro solishtirildi. *B.thuringiensis* 1fo shtamining 16S rRNK, cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlariga asoslangan filogenetik shajaralari MEGA-X dasturi orqali tuzildi. (version 10.1.8) [15].

Laboratoriya kolleksiyasidan tanlab olingan *B.thuringiensis* 1fo shtammi ustida tadqiqotlar olib borildi. Birinchi navbatda, mazkur shtamning o'ziga xos bo'lgan kristall oqsil siztez qilishi mikroskopik tahlilda namoyon bo'ldi. O'z navbatida bu kristall oqsillar turli xil xasharotlarga toksiklik xususiyatlarini namoyon qiladi. Shundan so'ng, Bt1fo shtamining 16S rDNK geni bo'yicha identifikatsiya qilish, cry va vip genlarini aniqlash uchun birlamchi PZR tahlilini amalga

o'shinish uchun jami 24 ta praymerlar dizayn qilindi va siztez qilinib PZR amplifikatsiyasi amalga oshirildi. Bunda dastlab modifikatsiyalangan Marmur usuli yordamida Bt1fo shtammidan genom DNK si ajratildi (1A-rasm).

2A-rasmda ko'ringanidek, *B.thuringiensis* Ifo shtammidan yuqori sifatli va toza genom DNK modifikatsiyalangan Marmur usuli yordamida ajratildi. 2B-rasmda ushbu bakteriyaning 16S rDNK genining taxminan 1500 bp hosil bo'ldi. Ushbu Bt 1fo ning 16S rDNK genining sekvenslangan mahsuloti 1443 bp, cry1Aa geni 1842 bp va cry1Ac geni esa 1465 bp bo'lib, ushbu genlar NCBI BLAST ma'lumotlar bazasidagi bakteriya turlarining 16S rDNK va cry genlari bilan o'zaro solishtirildi. Natijada, shtammning 16S rDNK geni tahliliga ko'ra mazkur shtamm *B.bombysepticus*, *B.cereus*, *B.subtilis*, *B.thuringiensis* kabi turlar bilan 99,51% o'xshash ekanligi aniqlandi.

Shundan so'ng, Mega4 bioinformatik dasturining Maximum-likelihood statistik usuli yordamida Bt1fo shtammning 16S rDNK, cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlariga asosanib filogenetik shajaralari tuzib chiqildi. Bt1fo shtammi 16S rDNK geni bo'yicha *B.toyonensis*, *B.bombysepticus*, *B.cereus*, *B.subtilis*, *B.thuringiensis* turlari bilan o'zaro solishtirildi (3-rasm).

3-Rasm. *B.thuringiensis Ifo* shtammining 16S rDNK geni bo'yicha tuzilgan filogenetik shajarasi.

Mega4 bioinformatik programmasining Maximum-likelihood statistik usulidan foydalanildi. *B.thuringiensis Ifo* shtammining 16S rDNK geni filogenetik shajarasi ko'ra, mazkur shtamm *B.cereus* va boshqa turlardan farq qilishi, hamda *B.thuringiensis* turi bilan bir xil ekanligi aniqlandi. Adabiyotlardan ma'lumki, universal primerlarga asoslangan 16S rDNK gen ketma-ketligi *B.cereus* va *B.thuringiensis* o'rtasida yuqori o'xshashlikni ya'ni 99% ni ko'rsatadi [16]. Bu o'xshashlikka qaramay, *B.thuringiensis* turlari o'ziga xos bo'lgan kristall va Vip oqsillarni kodlovchi genlari bilan *B.cereus* va boshqa turlar bilan ajralib turadi [17].

So'ngra, Bt1fo shtammida cry va vip oilasiga tegishli genlarni aniqlash maqsadida PZR amplifikatsiyasi amalga oshirildi. Bunda, cry1-8 va vip1, 2, 3 oilasi genlarini aniqlovchi praymerlardan foydalandi.

4-rasm. Bt 1fo shtammining cry va vip genlarining birlamchi PZR tahlili:

M-1kb DNK marker. 1- cry1, 2- cry2, 3- cry3, 4- cry4, 5- cry7-8, 6- Lep1, 7- Dip1, 8- cry3A, 9- vip1A, 10- vip2A, 11- vip3A, MM-Manfiy nazorat.

4-rasmdan ko'rinib turibdiki, Bt 1fo shtammida cry1, cry2 va Vip3 oilalariga tegishli bo'lgan Cry va Vip genlari mavjudligi aniqlandi. 6-qatordagi Lep1 praymerlari hosil qilgan PZR maxsuloti esa mazkur shtammida cry1 oilasining cry1Aa, cry1Ab va cry1Ac genlari borligini yana bir bor tasdiqladi. Shuningdek, Bt1fo shtammida cry3, cry4, cry7-8 va vip1A, vip2A genlari uchramasligi birlamchi PZR tahliliga ko'ra tasdiqlandi.

cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlari esa NCBI BLAST ma'lumotlar bazasidagi cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlar bilan 100% o'xshash ekanligi namoyon bo'ldi. Mazkur Bt 1fo shtammini kristal oqsillarini hosil qilishi va ushbu oqsillarni kodlovchi bir nechta genlari uchrashligiga qarab, bu shtamm *Bacillus thuringiensis* ekanligi tasdiqlandi va biz *B.thuringiensis* 1fo deb nomladik.

So'ngra, Mega4 bioinformatik dasturining Maximum-likelihood statistik usuli yordamida Bt1fo shtamining cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlariga asoslanib filogenetik shajarasi tuzib chiqildi. Bt1fo shtamining cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlari bo'yicha NCBI bazasidan cry1A oilasining cry1Aa, cry1Ab va cry1Ac genlari bilan taqqoslandi va filogenetik shajaralari tuzildi. cry2A geni esa outgroup sifatida tanlandi (5-rasm).

Filogenetik shajarasidan ko'rinib turibdiki, *B.thuringiensis* 1fo shtamining cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlari NCBI BLAST natijasi bilan bir xil ko'rsatkichni ya'ni bu ikkila gen ham cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlariga ta'luqli ekanligi tasdiqlandi. Bunda, Bt1fo shtamining cry1Aa geni 100% o'xshashlik bilan filogenetik daraxtning cry1Aa guruhi ichida joylashgani va xuddi shu ko'rsatkich bilan *Bt1fo* shtamining cry1Ac geni 100% o'xshashlik bilan filogenetik daraxtning cry1Aa guruhi ichida joylashgani namoyon bo'ldi. Adabiyotlardan ma'lumki, *B.thuringiensis* serovar *kurstaki* HD1 shtamida beshtagacha cry genlari (cry1Aa, cry1Ab, cry1Ac, cry2Aa va cry2Ab) uchrashligi aniqlangan [18].

5-rasm. *B.thuringiensis* 1fo shtamining cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlarining filogenetik shajarasi

Bizning Bt1fo shtamimizda esa cry1 oilasiga tegishli cry1Aa va cry1Ac genlari va vip3A geni mavjud ekanligi tadqiqotlarimiz natijasi namoyon bo'ldi. Bundan tashqari, mazkur shtamda cry2 oilasi genlari ham borligi aniqlangan bo'lib, keyingi tadqiqotlarimizda bu oila genlarini va boshqa genlarni aniqlash ustida tadqiqotlarimizni davom ettiramiz.

B.thuringiensis 1fo shtamining ko'sak qurti lichinkalariga qarshi faolligini baholash: Bt1fo asosli biopreparati (Spora va kristalli) ko'sak qurti lichinkalariga selder o'simligiga sepib oziqlantirildi. Tajribada 50 dona 2-3 yoshli lichinkalardan foydalanildi va bir hafta davomida kuzatildi. Nazoratda esa 10 ta shu yoshdagi lichinkalar kuzatildi (6-rasm).

A

B

6-Rasm. A- *Helicoverpa armigera* hasharotining sog'lom lichinkasi, **B-** *B.thuringiensis* 1fo asosli preparatdan nobud bo'lgan *Helicoverpa armigera* lichinkasi.

Tajribaning 7 kungiga kelib Bt1fo asosli biopreparat bilan oziqlantirilgan 50 dona ko'sak qurti lichinkalarining barchasi (100%) nobud bo'lganligi kuzatildi. Nazoratdagi lichinkalar esa 10 kunga kelib barchasi (100%) g'umkaka ketdi va 23-26 kunda urug'landi.

Hozirgi kunda o'simliklarni zararkunanda hasharotlardan himoya qilishning eng samarali yo'llardan biri biologik agentlardan foydalanishdir. Biz tadqiqot olib borgan *B.thuringiensis* 1fo bakteriyasi ham xuddi shunday samarali shtamlardandir. Tadqiqotlar davomida mazkur shtamm 16S rDNK geni bo'yicha molekulyar genetik identifikatsiya qilindi. Uning birlamchi PZR tahlili va sekvens natijalariga ko'ra, Bt 1fo shtammida cry1 oilasining cry1Aa, cry1Ac va vip3A genlari mavjudligi, hamda cry2 oilasi genlari ham uchrashligi aniqlandi va ushbu genlar NCBI ma'lumotlar bazasidagi cry va vip genlari bilan o'zaro taqqoslanib, filogenetik daraxtlari tuzib chiqildi. Shundan so'ng, Bt1fo shtammni *Helicoverpa armigera* lichinkalariga nisbatan faolligi o'rganilganda. Bt1fo asosli preparat bilan oziqlantirilganda *Helicoverpa armigera* ning 2-3 yoshli lichinkalari 7 kunga kelib 100% nobud bo'lganligi kuzatildi. Bt1fo shtammni qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarini *Helicoverpa armigera* kabi hasharotlardan himoya qilish uchun samarali bioagent sifatida foydalanish mumkin. Bt1fo shtammida mavjud cry1Aa, cry1Ac va vip3A genlarini mavjudligi, yaqin kelajakda transgen o'simliklarini yaratish imkoniyatlarini beradi.

REFERENCES

1. Salehi Jouzani G, Abad AP, Seifinejad A, Marzban R, Kariman K, Maleki B (2008a) Distribution and diversity of dipteran-specific cry and cyt genes in native *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains obtained from different ecosystems of Iran. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol* 35:83–94. doi:10.1007/s10295-007-0269-6.
2. Salehi Jouzani G, Seifinejad A, Saeezadeh A, Nazarian A, Yousefloo M, Soheilvand S, Mousivand M, Jahangiri R, Yazdani M, Amiri RM, Akbari S (2008b) Molecular detection of nematicidal crystalliferous *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains of Iran and evaluation of their toxicity on free-living and plant-parasitic.
3. Abdelmalek N, Sellami S, BenKridis A, Tounsi S, Rouis S (2015) Molecular characterisation of *Bacillus thuringiensis* strain MEB4 highly toxic to the Mediterranean flour moth *Ephestia kuehniella* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). *Pest Manag Sci*. doi:10.1002/ps.4066.
4. Zhou, Y., Wu, Z., Zhang, J., Wan, Y., Jin, W., Li, Y., Fang, X., 2020. Cry80Aa1, a novel *Bacillus thuringiensis* toxin with mosquitocidal activity to *Culex pipiens pallens*. *J. Invertebr. Pathol.* 173, 107386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2020.107386>.

5. da Silva, K.B., da Silva, C.B., Lisboa Ribeiro Júnior, K.A., de Freitas, J.M.D., de Freitas, J. D., Sanchez Chia, G., Salles Tinoco, R., da Costa, J.G., Fonseca Goulart, H., Goulart Santana, A.E., 2019. Morphology and distribution of antennal sensilla of *Automeris liberia* (Lepidoptera: Saturniidae). *Micron*. 123, 102682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2019.102682>.
6. Lackus, N.D., et al., 2019. Identification and characterization of trans-isopentenyl diphosphate synthases involved in herbivory-induced volatile terpene formation in *Populus trichocarpa*. *Molecules* (Basel, Switzerland). 24.
7. Graham, S.H., et al., 2019. Behavioral Responses of Thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and Tarnished Plant Bug (Hemiptera: Miridae) to a New Bt Toxin, Cry51Aa2.834_16 in Cotton. *J. Econ. Entomol.* 112, 1695–1704.
8. Francisco Salvà-Serra, Liselott Svensson-Stadler, Antonio Busquets, Daniel Jaén-Luchoro, Roger Karlsson, Edward R. B. Moore & Margarita Gomila Culture Collection University of Gothenburg (CCUG). A protocol for extraction and purification of high-quality and quantity bacterial DNA applicable for genome sequencing: a modified version of the Marmur procedure. *Method in Protocol Exchange* · August 2018. DOI: 10.1038/protex.2018.084.
9. Isolation and identification of *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains native of the Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia. Amina A. Hassan, Mohamed A. Youssef, M. M. A. Elashokhy, I. M. Ismail, Munirah Aldayel and Eman Afkar. *Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control* (2021) 31:6 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41938-020-00352-8>.
10. Carozzi NB, Kramer VC, Warren GW, Evola S, Koziel MC (1991) Prediction of insecticidal activity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains by polymerase chain reaction product profiles. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 57:3057–3061.
11. Shi Y, Xu W, Yuan M, Tang M, Chen J, Pang Y (2004) Expression of vip1/vip2 genes in *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus thuringiensis* and analysis of their signal peptides. *J Appl Microbiol* 97:757–765.
12. Estruch JJ, Warren GW, Mullins MA, Nye GJ, Craig JA, Koziel MG (1996) vip3A, a novel *Bacillus thuringiensis* vegetative insecticidal protein with a wide spectrum activities against lepidopteran insects. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 93:5389–5394.
13. Lane DJ (1991) 16S/23S rRNA sequencing. In: Stackebrandt E, Goodfellow M. *Nucleic acid techniques in bacterial systematics*. New York, N.Y.: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. pp. 115-176.
14. HB-09010031114358_PCard_QQ_PCR_Gel_Cleanup_Kit_0718_WW%20 (1) pdf.
15. Tamura K, Dudley J, Nei M, Kumar S. MEGA4: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) software version 4.0. *Mol Biol Evol.* 2007; 24: 1596–1599. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msm092> PMID:17488738.
16. Böhm, M.-E., Huptas, C., Krey, V. M., and Scherer, S. (2015). Massive horizontal gene transfer, strictly vertical inheritance and ancient duplications differentially shape the evolution of *Bacillus cereus* enterotoxin operons hbl, cytK and nhe. *BMC Evol. Biol.* 15:246. doi: 10.1186/s12862-015-0529-4.
17. Osman, G., Already, R., Assaedi, A., Organji, S., El-Ghareeb, D., Abulreesh, H., et al. (2015). Bioinsecticide *Bacillus thuringiensis* a comprehensive review. *Egyptian J. Biol. Pest Control.* 25, 271–288.

18. Ben-Dov, E.Zaritsky, A.Dahan, E.Barak, D.Sinai, R.Manasherob, R.Khamraev, A.Triotskaya, E. Dubitsky, A.Berezina, N. et al. Extended screening by PCR for seven cry-group genes from field-collected strains of *Bacillus thuringiensis*. Appl. Environ. Microbiol. 1997. 63, 4883–4890.